

requires C, 76.88; H, 9.46 per cent.) B.P. $181^{\circ}/1$ mm.; $202^{\circ}/9$ mm.; $n_D^{28.5}$, 1.5100; n_D^{10} , 1.5136; unsaturation number, 1.90. The substance is thick and syrupy in nature and insoluble in water. It smells exactly like Guerbet's acid. The silver salt is insoluble in water and is fairly stable towards light at ordinary temperature.

This is a weak acid and cannot be correctly titrated with alkali. Equivalent weight was found by ignition of the silver salt. (Found: Equiv., 233.9 $C_{15}H_{22}O_2$ requires Equiv., 234.49).

Methyl ester $C_{15}H_{21}O_2$ (CH_3) was prepared from the silver salt and methyl iodide in the usual way; b.p. $157^{\circ}/9$ mm.; n_D^{25} , 1.4969; n_D^{20} , 1.4989. (Found: C, 77.6; H, 9.77. $C_{15}H_{24}O_2$ requires C, 77.38; H, 9.7 per cent).

Absorption spectrum was determined by following the same procedure as in the case of Guerbet's acid (*cf.* Part IV).

Further work for the complete elucidation of the structure of this compound is in progress.

The author's thanks are due to the Government of Mysore for kindly supplying some sandalwood oil for further investigation of this substance as also that of Guerbet's acid. The author is also indebted to Prof. P. C. Guha for his interest during the investigation.

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STUDIES IN THE SANTALOL SERIES. PART VI. A NOTE ON THE PARACHOR OF FUSED RING STRUCTURE

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Only a limited amount of work has been done about the parachor of compounds containing fused ring structures with some of the carbon atoms being common to more than one ring. Deshapande and others (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 19, 157) by using *isonitrosocamphor* in nitrobenzene solution have proved the additive nature of parachor in fused-ring compounds.

Substances more complicated than *isonitrosocamphor* are easily obtainable among the compounds of the santalol series. In connection with our researches in the santalol series, the parachor of a typical compound of this series *viz.* that of the methyl ester of *tricyclo-ekasantalic acid* has been determined. The substance possesses a fused tricyclic ring structure and is a liquid under ordinary conditions. The pure ester was prepared according to the method of Semmler (*Ber.*, 1907, 40, 1120, 1124), b.p. $127^{\circ}/10$ mm.; n_D^{20} , 1.4785; d_4^{20} , 1.0166; Molecular formula $C_{13}H_{20}O_2$; Mol. Wt. 208.29. Surface tension of the substance was determined by the drop method, Traube's stalagmometer being used for this purpose, pure bi-distilled water was used as the reference liquid. Density of the ester at different temperatures was determined with a very small pycnometer; parachor was calculated in the usual way.

Temp.	Surface tension of ester.	Mol. Wt.	Density.	Parachor (P)	Mean (P)
20°	34.59	208.29	1.0166	407.7	497.0
30°	33.47	208.26	1.00737	496.3	

The theoretical value of parachor was calculated in the usual way from the structure of methyl ester of tricycloekasantalic acid (I).

Calculated parachor :

13C	4.8 × 13 =	62.4
20H	17.1 × 20 =	342.0
O ₂ (in ester)	60 =	60.0
1 three-membered ring	=	16.7
2 five-membered rings	8.5 × 2 =	17.0
		Total = 498.1

Thus the theoretically calculated value is found to agree closely with that obtained from the surface tension of the substance. Therefore, it can be concluded that in the parachor of a compound containing fused ring structure, all the rings play their parts separately as independent units, the carbon atoms common to more than one ring having no additional influence whatsoever.

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